

IMPACT OF AN INFORMATION ENVIRONMENT TO SOCIETY**Mahmudova S.***Nakhchivan State University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10581956>**Abstract**

The article includes the essence and part of the development of the Data Society in the early XXI century and marked that the method of organizing the Data Society covers financially established states. Azerbaijan also hosted the organization of "Data Society" and the Republic has won a great victory in this matter. The article says that in the XXI century and the open need for its trade is an invaluable part of the progress of the leading society today.

Keywords: information, communities, internet, integration, information area

In the early 1960s, the concept of "Information Society" in Japan has been the fore and has been the subject of theoretical and scientific research for more than fifty years. The main philosophical objectives of the information society are generally to meet the needs of information and knowledge and strengthen their social communication between them, spreading their ideas and knowledge to the general public. The main purpose of this method is to then solve social problems and create rich information that can be used to promote human progress.

In other word, the information society is a society that the vast majority of people use modern information technology for creating, transfer, processing and storage of information, and above all, in the purest form of information. The main priority of the state is an information society. One of the main goals of the state policy of the independent Republic of Azerbaijan is the creation of an information society. In recent years, information technologies in society are observed significantly due to the sustainable and thoughtful initiatives implemented in this area.

Many important achievements that have prosecuted all areas of human activity in the modern information society have been possible through the rapid development of new "computer and information" technologies, digital and telecommunications technologies and other factors. The establishment of a successful industrial technological revolution and the latest computer technologies in the third decade of the XXI century is the result of the global integration process, which covers the whole world today. With its amnesty, he hopes to build the first high-speed Synchronous information technology in the world.

The foundation of the work carried out in the direction of building an "information society" in Azerbaijan was laid by the "National Strategy on Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of the Republic of Azerbaijan" approved by the Decree of the great leader Heydar Aliyev dated February 17, 2003, and the main goal of this Strategy is "the development of information and communication technologies is to help the democratic development of the country and ensure the transition to the information society by using it widely.

Overall, increased efficiency, lower costs, electronic document exchange in government agencies, e-

commerce systems, and high-quality goods and services are the benefits of the country's increasing digitization. A society devoted mainly to the creation, storage, processing and use of information is called an information society. In the information society, people and groups must collect, process and analyze certain information before making decisions. The amount of information has increased so much that one person cannot process it by himself. For this, special technical means are required for this work.

The process of computerization of society ensures the transition from industrial society to information society. The process of computerization of the society gives every member of the society the opportunity to receive information according to his needs. Until recently, people used the word "information" instead of "computerization". However, the word "computerization" refers to the development and application of computer technology. Social computerization is a broader concept than computerization. Therefore, today, not the technical means, but the goals and essence of the socio-technical process are more important. Computerization is a component of the computerization process, its technical basis.

In modern age, it is difficult to give a precise definition of the concept of "information". In encyclopedic publications, it is said that the concept of "information" comes from the Latin word "informati". From the point of view of materialist philosophy, information is perceived and evaluated as a description of the real world using information. Information can be audio, text, images, digital indicators, graphs, tables, etc. In modern times, information is considered one of the main driving forces of human society as a very important resource. It exists independently of our perception and is reflected in our perception as a result of reading, receiving in the form of signals, interaction of stimuli.

In the case of multiform information, all material exists in one object and becomes something else through the process of movement. In studying the process of computerization that occurs in the physical world living nature and human life, scientific resources can be obtained and obtained. In addition, information is conceptually given in "informatics" science.

Informatics, which separated from cybernetics and became an independent scientific field in the middle of the last century, is characterized by the methods of cre-

ating, receiving, processing and transmitting information. Although information in the general scientific sense reflects the exchange of information between people, as well as between people and devices, and signals of animate and inanimate nature, there are still different definitions.

The share of the mass media in conveying the information and events happening in the country and around the world to the society is checked. By playing the role of witness and member in complex forms, the mass media guarantee the delivery of information to the society. The mass media's ability to advise, educate, engage is enough to prove its role in the progress of society. Mass media speak their case by informing the society. In advanced times, mass media means radio, television, conventional media (daily newspapers, magazines) and the Internet. Mass media reflect open life and ICT becomes a means of communication between individuals, government agencies and society in general. Mass media, as a "reflection" of society, play an important role in issues of public power, political forms, character, as well as public and social issues. In the most advanced world, the mass media, in addition to being a means of propaganda and instruction, occupy an imperative place in the management of social-political and socio-economic forms.

Currently, the improvement of all its areas is related to the development of the mental abilities of information assets and the extensive use of information assets. In extension, individuals should be familiar with the current state of personal computers and the Internet, the possible outcomes and application ranges of advanced information and communication advances, and the science and information industry field of information innovation. Innovation use area, information innovation level to government members, primarily to science and instruction. It is considered one of the most important imperatives before the system.

Data is one of the most important system-shaping variables in an advanced society. Another reason why data corruption is so high is related to the professionalism of its use. It lacks a clear understanding of how to control large areas of data and how to control any area of social governance.

We conclude that, regardless of geography, the modern "information society" involves satisfying everyone's need for all kinds of knowledge and comprehensive information, developing an interpersonal communication environment, and rapidly providing the public with the latest information.

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